

COMPARISON OF THE PATTERN OF ELECTROLYTE IMBALANCE IN DIABETIC PATIENTS WITH AND WITHOUT GLYCEMIC CONTROL

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Abstract

Background: Electrolyte imbalances frequently complicate type 2 diabetes and increase the risk of morbidity. Evidence on how glycemic control shapes these disturbances remains limited in Pakistan.

Methods: We carried out a cross-sectional study of 136 adults with type 2 diabetes attending a tertiary care hospital in Bahawalpur. We recorded demographic and clinical characteristics, measured serum electrolytes, and assessed glycemic status using HbA1c. We compared the prevalence of sodium and potassium disturbances between patients with and without glycemic control and examined associations with comorbidities and duration of disease.

Results: Most participants were aged 61–80 years (69.1%), and nearly seven in ten had poor glycemic control. Hyponatremia (39.7%) and hypokalemia (34.6%) were the most frequent abnormalities, followed by hyperkalemia (25.7%) and hypernatremia (15.4%). Hyponatremia occurred more often in patients with longer duration of diabetes, poor glycemic control, and hypertension ($p < 0.05$). Hypernatremia was less common and showed a significant association only with lower educational status ($p = 0.01$). Hypokalemia was more frequent in younger patients and those with hypertension, while hyperkalemia was strongly associated with poor glycemic control, hypertension, and obesity ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Electrolyte disturbances were highly prevalent among patients with type 2 diabetes, with sodium and potassium abnormalities most prominent. Poor glycemic control and cardiometabolic comorbidities shaped these patterns. Regular monitoring of serum electrolytes alongside HbA1c may help clinicians prevent complications and improve outcomes in this high-risk population.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a group of metabolic disorders characterized by impaired carbohydrate metabolism, which causes reduced glucose utilization and persistent hyperglycemia. The diagnosis of diabetes mellitus is established based on defined criteria, which include: a haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c)

level of 6.5% or above, a fasting plasma glucose of at least 126 mg/dL (after no caloric intake for a minimum of 8 hours), a 2-hour plasma glucose level of 200 mg/dL or higher during an oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT), or a random plasma glucose level of 200 mg/dL or more in the presence of classic

symptoms of hyperglycemia.¹ The condition is characterized by either a partial or complete deficiency in insulin production and/or a reduced responsiveness of target tissues to the metabolic actions of insulin.² Diabetes mellitus has emerged as a major global public health concern, with its prevalence and burden steadily increasing in the absence of effective control measures. The rise is especially pronounced in urban populations, where lifestyle-related factors play a key role, leading many experts to describe the condition as a modern epidemic.³ Diabetes is a major cause of serious health complications, including kidney disease, myocardial infarction, stroke, vision loss, and lower limb amputations. Between 2000 and 2019, age-adjusted mortality rates from diabetes rose by 3%. By 2022, an estimated 26.7% of adults in Pakistan were living with diabetes, representing nearly 33 million cases nationwide.⁴ Electrolytes play an essential role in numerous physiological functions, such as regulating acid-base balance, maintaining membrane potential, enabling muscle contraction, facilitating nerve transmission, and controlling body fluid distribution.⁵

Insulin has been shown to stimulate the activity of the Na/K-ATPase enzyme. Consequently, reduced insulin levels result in diminished Na/K-ATPase function, leading to impaired sodium and potassium regulation. This disruption hinders transport across biological membranes and also restricts the absorption of monosaccharides by the intestinal epithelium.^{6,7} Electrolyte disturbances are associated with diabetes mellitus, as specific electrolytes are essential for intermediary metabolism and the proper functioning of cells.⁸ Electrolytes are fundamental for sustaining homeostasis, preserving cellular activity, supporting adequate tissue perfusion, and maintaining acid-base equilibrium. In type 1 diabetes mellitus, the most frequently affected electrolytes include sodium, potassium, calcium, and chloride, among others.^{9,10} Electrolyte disturbances in diabetes are associated with fluid shifts caused by hyperglycemia and with overall fluid loss resulting from osmotic diuresis.^{11,12} A study done by Seed et al found the hyponatremia, hypernatremia, hypokalemia and hyperkalemia in diabetic patients to be 3.2%, 88.2%, 6.6% and 93.4% respectively.¹³ Electrolyte imbalances are common in diabetic

patients due to the complex interplay of hyperglycemia, insulin resistance, and associated renal dysfunction. Poor glycemic control exacerbates these imbalances by increasing osmotic diuresis, leading to significant losses of electrolytes such as sodium, potassium, and magnesium. Conversely, well-controlled diabetes may mitigate these disturbances, reducing the risk of complications such as arrhythmias, muscle weakness, and cognitive dysfunction. Understanding the patterns of electrolyte imbalance in patients with and without glycemic control is essential for improving clinical management and outcomes. This study aims to provide insights into how effective glycemic control influences electrolyte homeostasis, highlighting the importance of personalized diabetes management strategies to prevent complications and optimize patient care.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This cross-sectional study was carried out in the Department of Medicine at Bahawalpur Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur, from 15 January 2025 to 15 June 2025 following approval of the research synopsis. The study included 136 patients, calculated using WHO software based on a 6.6% prevalence of hypokalemia in diabetic patients, a 4% margin of error, and a 95% confidence level.¹³ A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was employed to recruit participants.

Eligible participants were men and women aged between 40 and 80 years with a documented history of type 2 diabetes mellitus for more than one year. Patients were excluded if they had a history of hyperthyroidism or hypothyroidism, were on anti-hyperlipidemic medications for dyslipidemia, had acute coronary syndrome, microvascular or macrovascular diabetic complications, stroke, asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, chronic renal failure, or chronic liver disease.

The study was initiated after obtaining approval from the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan and ethical clearance from the Bahawalpur Victoria Hospital Ethics Review Committee. Patients attending the outpatient department who met the inclusion criteria were invited to participate. Informed written consent was obtained after explaining the purpose of the study. A brief history

was taken to record demographic details, age, gender, and duration of diabetes.

Blood samples were collected by the principal investigator using a 5 cc disposable syringe, drawing 5 ml of venous blood during routine follow-up visits. Samples were appropriately labeled and transported to the hospital's standardized laboratory for analysis of HbA1c, serum sodium, and serum potassium. Glycemic control and electrolyte imbalance were determined in accordance with the operational definitions. All findings were recorded in a pre-designed proforma.

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20. Continuous variables, including age, serum sodium, serum potassium, height, weight, cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, HDL, duration of diabetes, and HbA1c, were summarized as mean and standard deviation for normally distributed data, as determined by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. For non-normally distributed variables, median and interquartile range (IQR) were reported. Categorical variables, such as gender, dyslipidemia, hypertension, smoking status, obesity status, occupational status, family monthly income, educational status, glycemic status, hyponatremia, hypernatremia, hypokalemia, and hyperkalemia, were presented as frequencies and percentages.

Comparisons of electrolyte imbalances between patients with and without glycemic control were made using the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, as appropriate. Stratification was performed for age, gender, dyslipidemia, hypertension, smoking status, obesity, occupational status, family monthly income, educational status, and duration of type 2 diabetes to assess their potential effect on the outcome variables. Post-stratification analysis was conducted using the Chi-square or Fisher's exact test, and a p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

We enrolled 136 patients with type 2 diabetes in this study. Most participants were between 61 and 80 years of age (69.1%), while 30.9% were in the 40-60 year group. Women accounted for just over half of the sample (51.5%). The majority had lived with diabetes for more than five years (70.6%), and nearly seven in ten (69.1%) showed poor glycemic control. Hypertension affected about a quarter of the cohort

(24.3%), whereas dyslipidemia (44.9%) and obesity (45.6%) were more common. More than one-third of participants reported smoking, and over 60% were unemployed. Educational attainment varied, with 10.3% illiterate and 39.7% having only primary education.

Electrolyte abnormalities appeared frequently. Hyponatremia was present in 39.7% of patients, making it the most common sodium disorder, while hypernatremia was less frequent at 15.4%. Disturbances in potassium were also notable: 34.6% had hypokalemia and 25.7% had hyperkalemia.¹³ These findings indicate that sodium and potassium imbalances affect a substantial proportion of diabetic patients presenting at our tertiary care hospital, with hyponatremia and hypokalemia occurring most often.

Hyponatremia showed clear associations with the chronicity of diabetes and comorbid conditions. Patients with more than five years' duration of diabetes were significantly more likely to have hyponatremia than those with a shorter history ($p=0.04$). Poor glycemic control was also strongly associated with hyponatremia ($p=0.01$). Similarly, patients with coexisting hypertension demonstrated a higher frequency of hyponatremia compared to non-hypertensive patients ($p=0.04$). Other characteristics such as age, sex, smoking status, obesity, and income did not show significant associations.

Hypernatremia displayed a different pattern. While slightly more common among those with poor glycemic control and longer disease duration, these differences were not statistically significant. Educational status, however, did show a strong relationship with hypernatremia ($p=0.01$). Patients with lower levels of education had a greater likelihood of hypernatremia than those with higher educational attainment, suggesting that health literacy may play a role in the prevention or recognition of this condition.

Potassium disorders revealed contrasting trends. Hypokalemia occurred more frequently in younger participants (40-60 years, $p=0.01$) and in those with hypertension ($p=0.05$), but did not vary significantly by glycemic control or diabetes duration. Hyperkalemia, on the other hand, showed strong associations with poor glycemic control ($p=0.01$), obesity ($p=0.01$), and hypertension ($p=0.04$). These

results suggest that while hypokalemia may be driven more by age and cardiovascular comorbidities, hyperkalemia is closely linked to metabolic disturbances in obese and poorly controlled diabetic patients.

DISCUSSION

This study shows that electrolyte imbalance is common among patients with type 2 diabetes presenting to a tertiary hospital in Bahawalpur. Hyponatremia and hypokalemia emerged as the most frequent abnormalities, while hypernatremia and hyperkalemia occurred less often. These results highlight the vulnerability of sodium and potassium regulation in diabetes, a finding that mirrors earlier studies from Ethiopia and India, where these electrolytes were also most frequently deranged in diabetic patients.^{14,17}

Hyponatremia was strongly associated with long-standing diabetes, poor glycemic control, and hypertension in our cohort. The relationship between hyperglycemia and sodium loss has been well documented. In Gondar, uncontrolled hyperglycemia increased the odds of electrolyte imbalance more than six-fold, with hyponatremia being the dominant abnormality.¹⁴ Similarly, a Karachi study found a clear inverse correlation between fasting blood glucose and serum sodium.¹⁵ Our findings also indicate that hypertension adds to this risk, possibly through nephropathy and activation of the renin-angiotensin system, mechanisms that previous studies have linked to sodium depletion in diabetic populations.¹⁵⁻¹⁷

Hypernatremia was less prevalent and showed weaker associations with clinical and metabolic characteristics. Only educational status demonstrated a significant link, with lower levels of schooling associated with higher prevalence. This association, although less frequently reported, may reflect the influence of health literacy on fluid management, dietary practices, and treatment adherence. Evidence from Ethiopia and Bangladesh has suggested that socioeconomic and behavioral factors influence electrolyte homeostasis, lending support to this interpretation.^{14,18} Unlike hyponatremia, which is largely driven by hyperglycemia, hypernatremia may result from inadequate fluid intake or unrecognized

osmotic diuresis, which disproportionately affects patients with limited health awareness.

Potassium disorders displayed a distinct pattern. Hypokalemia was more frequent in younger patients and in those with hypertension, while hyperkalemia clustered in obese patients and in those with poor glycemic control. These findings are consistent with studies from Ethiopia and India, which reported hypokalemia in younger diabetics and hyperkalemia in uncontrolled cases.^{14, 16} Insulin deficiency reduces intracellular potassium uptake, which may explain the link between poor glycemic control and hyperkalemia, while osmotic diuresis and insulin therapy may promote potassium depletion in other patients.^{16, 20} The coexistence of both abnormalities within the same cohort underlines the dynamic shifts in potassium balance that occur during the course of diabetes.

Overall, our results reinforce the evidence that electrolyte disturbances in diabetics are multifactorial and context-dependent. Sodium and potassium are consistently the most labile electrolytes, with hyponatremia marking the burden of chronic and uncontrolled disease, and hyperkalemia reflecting severe metabolic dysregulation. The consistency of these patterns across studies from South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa strengthens the argument for routine monitoring of electrolytes in diabetic care.^{14, 20} Integrating such monitoring into routine practice could help clinicians anticipate complications, tailor therapy, and improve long-term outcomes for patients with diabetes.

LIMITATIONS

We carried out this study in a single tertiary care hospital, which restricts the extent to which the results can be applied to other settings or populations. The cross-sectional design also prevents us from determining causal relationships between poor glycemic control and the observed electrolyte disturbances.

CONCLUSION

We found that electrolyte disturbances were common in patients with type 2 diabetes, with hyponatremia and hypokalemia occurring most frequently. Poor glycemic control, longer duration of disease, hypertension, and obesity shaped the pattern

of these imbalances, while hyperkalemia appeared closely linked to uncontrolled diabetes and obesity. These results highlight the need for clinicians to

monitor electrolytes regularly in diabetic patients in addition to routine glycemic assessment.

Table 1: Distribution of baseline characteristics among the study participants.

Variables	n (%)
Age	
40 to 60 years	42 (30.9)
61 to 80 years	94 (69.1)
Gender	
Male	66 (48.5)
Female	70 (51.5)
Duration of T2DM	
≤ 5 years	40 (29.4)
> 5 years	96 (70.6)
Glycemic control	
≤ 6.5	61 (44.9)
> 6.5	94 (69.1)
Hypertension	
Yes	33 (24.3)
No	103 (75.7)
Dyslipidemia	
Yes	61 (44.9)
No	75 (55.1)
Obesity status	
Yes	62 (45.6)
No	74 (54.4)
Smoking status	
Yes	50 (36.8)
No	86 (63.2)
Family monthly income status	
≤ 50000	63 (46.3)
> 50000	73 (53.7)
Occupational status	
Employed	53 (39.8)
Unemployed	80 (60.2)
Educational status	
Illiterate	14 (10.3)
Primary	54 (39.7)
Secondary	36 (26.5)
Higher	32 (23.5)
Hyponatremia	
Yes	54 (39.7)
No	82 (60.3)
Hypernatremia	
Yes	21 (15.4)

No	115 (84.6)
Hypokalemia	
Yes	47 (34.6)
No	89 (65.4)
Hyperkalemia	
Yes	35 (25.7)
No	101 (74.3)
Total	136 (100)

Table 2: Distribution of patient characteristics according to the hyponatremia groups.

Variables	Hyponatremia Yes n (%)	Hyponatremia No n (%)	P value
Age			0.10
40 to 60 years	21 (50)	21 (50)	
61 to 80 years	33 (35.1)	61 (64.9)	
Gender			0.78
Male	27 (40.9)	39 (59.1)	
Female	27 (38.6)	43 (61.4)	
Duration of T2DM			0.04
≤ 5 years	21 (52.5)	19 (47.5)	
> 5 years	33 (34.4)	63 (65.6)	
Glycemic control			0.01
≤ 6.5	13 (21.3)	48 (78.7)	
> 6.5	41 (54.7)	34 (45.3)	
Hypertension			0.04
Yes	18 (54.5)	15 (45.5)	
No	36 (35)	67 (65)	
Dyslipidemia			0.78
Yes	25 (41)	36 (59)	
No	29 (38.7)	46 (61.3)	
Obesity status			0.20
Yes	21 (33.9)	41 (66.1)	
No	33 (44.6)	41 (55.4)	
Smoking status			0.16
Yes	16 (32)	34 (68)	
No	38 (44.2)	48 (55.8)	
Family monthly income status			0.16
≤ 50000	29 (46)	34 (54)	
> 50000	25 (34.2)	48 (65.8)	

Occupational status			
Employed	24 (43.6)	31 (56.4)	0.44
Unemployed	30 (37)	51 (63)	
Educational status			
Illiterate	07 (50)	07 (50)	0.28
Primary	17 (31.5)	37 (68.5)	
Secondary	18 (50)	18 (50)	
Higher	12 (37.5)	20 (62.5)	

Table 3: Distribution of patient characteristics according to the hypernatremia groups.

Variables	Hypernatremia Yes n (%)	Hypernatremia No n (%)	P value
Age			0.44
40 to 60 years	05 (11.9)	37 (88.1)	
61 to 80 years	16 (17)	78 (83)	
Gender			0.29
Male	08 (12.1)	58 (87.9)	
Female	13 (18.6)	57 (81.4)	
Duration of T2DM			0.14
≤ 5 years	09 (22.5)	31 (77.5)	
> 5 years	12 (12.5)	84 (87.5)	
Glycemic control			0.63
≤ 6.5	07 (11.5)	54 (88.5)	
> 6.5	14 (18.7)	61 (81.3)	
Hypertension			0.29
Yes	07 (21.2)	26 (78.8)	
No	14 (13.6)	89 (86.4)	
Dyslipidemia			0.45
Yes	11 (18)	50 (82)	
No	10 (13.3)	65 (86.7)	
Obesity status			0.83
Yes	10 (16.1)	52 (83.9)	
No	11 (14.9)	63 (85.1)	
Smoking status			0.39
Yes	06 (12)	44 (88)	
No	15 (17.4)	71 (82.6)	

Family monthly income status ≤ 50000 > 50000	09 (14.3) 12 (16.4)	54 (85.7) 61 (83.6)	0.72
Occupational status Employed Unemployed	07 (12.7) 14 (17.3)	48 (87.3) 67 (82.7)	0.47
Educational status Illiterate Primary Secondary Higher	04 (28.6) 14 (25.9) 03 (8.3) 00 (00)	10 (71.4) 40 (74.1) 33 (91.7) 32 (100)	0.01

Table 4: Distribution of patient characteristics according to the hypokalemia groups.

Variables	Hypokalemia Yes n (%)	Hypokalemia No n (%)	P value
Age 40 to 60 years 61 to 80 years	21 (50) 26 (27.7)	21 (50) 68 (72.3)	0.01
Gender Male Female	21 (31.8) 26 (37.1)	45 (68.2) 44 (62.9)	0.51
Duration of T2DM ≤ 5 years > 5 years	13 (32.5) 34 (35.4)	27 (67.5) 62 (64.5)	0.74
Glycemic control ≤ 6.5 > 6.5	20 (32.8) 27 (36)	41 (67.2) 48 (64)	0.69
Hypertension Yes No	16 (48.5) 31 (30.1)	17 (51.5) 72 (69.9)	0.05
Dyslipidemia Yes No	22 (36.1) 25 (33.3)	39 (63.9) 50 (66.7)	0.73
Obesity status Yes No	20 (32.3) 27 (36.5)	42 (67.7) 47 (63.5)	0.60

Smoking status			
Yes	15 (30)	35 (70)	0.39
No	32 (37.2)	54 (62.8)	
Family monthly income status			
≤ 50000	20 (31.7)	43 (68.3)	0.52
> 50000	27 (37)	46 (63)	
Occupational status			
Employed	18 (32.7)	37 (67.3)	0.71
Unemployed	29 (35.8)	52 (64.2)	
Educational status			
Illiterate	06 (42.9)	08 (57.1)	0.62
Primary	21 (38.9)	33 (61.1)	
Secondary	10 (27.8)	26 (72.2)	
Higher	10 (31.2)	22 (68.8)	

Table 5: Distribution of patient characteristics according to the hyperkalemia groups.

Variables	Hyperkalemia Yes n (%)	Hyperkalemia No n (%)	P value
Age			0.17
40 to 60 years	14 (33.3)	28 (66.7)	
61 to 80 years	21 (22.3)	73 (77.7)	
Gender			0.43
Male	15 (22.7)	51 (77.3)	
Female	20 (28.6)	50 (71.4)	
Duration of T2DM			0.76
≤ 5 years	11 (27.5)	29 (72.5)	
> 5 years	24 (25)	72 (75)	
Glycemic control			0.01
≤ 6.5	28 (45.9)	33 (54.1)	
> 6.5	07 (9.3)	68 (90.7)	
Hypertension			0.04
Yes	04 (12.1)	29 (87.9)	
No	31 (30.1)	72 (69.9)	
Dyslipidemia			0.78
Yes	15 (24.6)	46 (75.4)	
No	20 (26.7)	55 (73.3)	

Obesity status			
Yes	23 (37.1)	39 (62.9)	0.01
No	12 (16.2)	62 (83.8)	
Smoking status			
Yes	12 (24)	38 (76)	0.72
No	23 (26.7)	63 (73.3)	
Family monthly income status			
≤ 50000	12 (19)	51 (81)	0.09
> 50000	23 (31.5)	50 (68.5)	
Occupational status			
Employed	16 (29.1)	39 (70.9)	0.46
Unemployed	19 (2.35)	62 (76.5)	
Educational status			
Illiterate	03 (21.4)	11 (78.6)	0.01
Primary	25 (46.3)	29 (53.7)	
Secondary	00 (00)	36 (100)	
Higher	07 (21.9)	25 (78.1)	

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